

FOUR-BAND IMAGING SPECTROPOLARIMETRY OF THE LUNAR PYROCLASTIC DEPOSIT NEAR RIMA BODE AND THE IMPACT MELT SHEET AND EJECTA OF TYCHO. C. Wöhler¹, M. Bhatt², D. Misra^{2,3}, D. Dhingra⁴ ¹Image Analysis Group, TU Dortmund University, Dortmund, Germany, christian.woehler@tu-dortmund.de; ²Physical Research Laboratory, Ahmedabad 380009, India; ³Indian Institute of Technology Gandhinagar, Gandhinagar 382055, India; ⁴Dept. of Earth Sciences, Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur, Kanpur 208016, India.

Introduction: Imaging polarimetry is a well-established, though often neglected, method for analysing the structural properties of the lunar regolith (e.g., [1, 2]). Lunar glasses are widely distributed and important for understanding the physical properties of fine-grained regolith [3]. These glasses may originate from volcanic eruption or from impact processes. Because compositionally these glasses are similar, imaging polarimetry is appropriate for discriminating them based on their physical properties. In this work, we compare two presumably glass-rich lunar areas in terms of their spectropolarimetric properties: the Rima Bode pyroclastic deposit [4] and the impact melt sheet of the crater Tycho [5]. We will point out common characteristics and differences between the spectropolarimetric properties of these lithounits.

Data and Methods: Data of the Rima Bode and Tycho regions were acquired at five different phase angles between 4° and 30° with a telescope of 430 mm aperture at the Mount Abu Observatory, Physical Research Laboratory, in Rajasthan, India,

using an industrial-grade grayscale polarisation camera combined with standard astronomical BVRI Johnson-Cousins broadband filters centered around wavelengths of 430, 520, 632 and 890 nm. Additional observations at 86° (both regions) and 52° (Rima Bode) were conducted with a telescope of 200 mm aperture located near Dortmund, Germany, equipped with the same camera and filters [6]. The inferred images of the degree of linear polarisation (DoLP) were georeferenced, and the empirical function of [7] was fitted to each pixel, allowing for the derivation of the parameters α_{inv} (phase angle at which the DoLP phase curve $P(\alpha)$ has a zero crossing), the maximum DoLP $P_{\text{max}} > 0$, the phase angle α_{max} at which P_{max} occurs, the minimum DoLP $P_{\text{min}} < 0$ occurring at phase angles between 0° and α_{inv} , the phase angle α_{min} at which P_{min} occurs, and the slope h of $P(\alpha)$ at $\alpha = \alpha_{\text{inv}}$ [1, 2].

The Umov law states that P_{max} decreases with increasing albedo A [1]. As a proxy for A , we used the calibrated spectral reflectance of the Moon Mineralogy Mapper (M³) instrument [8] at 890 nm wavelength [9, 10, 11] for Rima Bode, and the measured

Fig. 1: Spectropolarimetric analysis of the Rima Bode region. (a) Polarisation excess E , showing positive anomalies for the pyroclastic deposits near Rima Bode (bottom centre) and in Sinus Aestuum (upper right). (b) RGB colour composite depicting the scores on the first three principal components of the spectropolarimetric dataset. (c) Cluster index map. (d) Cluster prototypes, with curve colours corresponding to the cluster colours in (c).

intensity at 86° phase angle for Tycho (due to topographic artifacts in the M³ data of this region). To the $\log P$ vs. $\log A$ values of each region we fitted a polynomial $p_n(\log A)$ of degree n . The Umov law does not describe the P_{\max} vs. A behaviour perfectly, and the pixel-wise “excess polarisation” $E = \log P - p_n(\log A)$ indicates that the regolith grain size is above average for $E > 0$ and below average for $E < 0$ [1]. We set $n = 1$ for Rima Bode and $n = 2$ for Tycho.

We then applied a principal component analysis (PCA) [12] to our 24-dimensional data set and constructed an RGB composite of the scores on the first three (Rima Bode) and two (Tycho) principal components, respectively. Clustering this three-dimensional dataset with a self-organizing map (SOM) [12] provides an unsupervised segmentation of the study area into nine classes and the corresponding prototypes.

Results: The clustering analysis of the spectropolarimetric parameters yields a clear segmentation of both the Rima Bode pyroclastic deposit and the Tycho impact melt sheet, ejecta blanket, and ray pattern. The pyroclastic deposit and impact melt both show a positive polarisation excess anomaly but are distinguishable by their spectropolarimetric characteristics.

Rima Bode. The pyroclastic deposit shows a positive polarisation excess E (Fig. 1a). The PCA (Fig. 1b) and clustering analysis (Fig. 1c) identify the pyroclastic material as distinct from the undisturbed mare to the north, the mare covered by ejecta from crater Copernicus to the west and northwest, and the

highland to the east and southeast. The variability of the cluster prototypes is low for α_{inv} , P_{min} , and α_{min} . The pyroclastic material stands out by its very high P_{min} value.

Tycho. In a ring-shaped area around Tycho it is $E > 0$, whereas $E < 0$ for the continuous ejecta blanket as mapped in [4] and the prominent rays (Fig. 2a). The PCA (Fig. 2b) and clustering analysis (Fig. 2c) reveal a large area around Tycho (clusters 7 and 8, orange and red) that largely coincides with the continuous ejecta blanket, plus a conspicuous ray pattern. Cluster 6 (yellow) and in part also cluster 9 (brown) coincide with the area found in [4] to exhibit a high density of impact melt structures. The other clusters denote the highlands west of Tycho. The melt sheet and ejecta are inconspicuous regarding their P_{max} values, while they stand out as particularly high in α_{max} and low in $|P_{\text{min}}|$ and α_{inv} .

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Fig. 2: Spectropolarimetric analysis of the region around the crater Tycho and west of it. (a) Polarisation excess E , showing a positive anomaly for the impact melt ring around the crater. (b) RGB colour composite depicting the scores on the first two principal components of the spectropolarimetric dataset. (c) Cluster index map. (d) Cluster prototypes, with curve colours corresponding to the cluster colours in (c). Cluster prototypes 3 and 5, corresponding to surface parts shadowed in the image data of the largest phase angle of 86° , have been omitted.

